

SCOPING REVIEW PROTOCOL

Applications of Agent-Based Modeling in Population Management and the Resilience of Dialysis Services in the Face of Disruptive Extreme Events: A Scoping Review

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INTRODUCTION

Disruptive extreme health events, such as floods, blackouts, heat waves, blizzards, hurricanes, and severe storms, affect the continuity of healthcare, especially in clinically vulnerable populations, such as people with chronic kidney disease (CKD) dependent on hemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis^{1,2}. The interruption of transportation, energy, water supply, supplies, and staffing can compromise access to treatment and increase the risk of complications and mortality^{3,4,5}. Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) models have been used to simulate interactions between individuals, services, infrastructure, and logistical flows, allowing the exploration of complex healthcare response scenarios. However, it is still unclear how this approach has been applied to the population management of renal patients and to the organization of resources in dialysis clinics in post-disaster scenarios.

This review is part of a research agenda dedicated to the development of agent-based simulation models for analyzing the resilience of dialysis services in the face of extreme environmental and technological events, an approach widely used to represent collective and territorial dynamics in complex risk and disaster response scenarios⁶. These findings should support the creation of territorial models that could be applied to the Brazilian context, with an emphasis on the continuity of renal replacement therapy, patient redistribution, and management of critical resources in scenarios of infrastructure disruption.

DEFINITIONS

In this protocol, the term "disruptive extreme events impacting dialysis services" will be adopted to describe situations that can compromise the continuity of renal care provision through disruptions in critical infrastructure, healthcare logistics, and territorial organization of health services. For the purposes of this review, the term includes:

- Extreme weather events (floods, heat waves, droughts, severe storms).
- Natural disasters (earthquakes, hurricanes, landslides).
- Technological disasters (power outages, critical infrastructure failures, water supply disruptions).
- Composite or cascading events involving multiple simultaneous failures of infrastructure, transportation, and essential services.

Epidemiological health emergencies, such as epidemics and pandemics (e.g., COVID-19), will not be included, as they present a temporal dynamic, mechanisms of healthcare impact, and response strategies distinct from those associated with extreme infrastructural and environmental events.

This operational definition will be used to guide the eligibility criteria, the search strategy and the synthesis of results.

RESEARCH QUESTION

How has ABM been used to support the population management of patients with kidney disease and in the organization of healthcare, workforce, and operational resources in dialysis services during extreme environmental and technological events that affect treatment continuity?

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To map and characterize studies that use Agent-Based Modeling to support population management in hemodialysis and to maintain the functioning of dialysis clinics during disruptive extreme health events.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To identify the types of disruptive extreme health events addressed in the studies.
- To describe the modeled renal populations.
- To characterize the components of the Agent-Based Models, including agents, environment, rules, inputs, and outputs.
- To identify which dialysis clinic resources and processes are simulated.
- To map the outcomes analyzed, such as continuity of care, access to dialysis, mortality, logistics, response time, and resource use.

- To identify methodological gaps and opportunities for the application of Agent-Based Modeling in nephrology and disaster response.

METHODS

Study design

Scoping review, conducted in accordance with the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis and reported following the PRISMA-ScR guidelines⁷.

PCC framework

PCC Criteria	Definition or justification
Participants	people with chronic kidney disease (CKD), kidney failure, advanced kidney disease, patients on hemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis, as well as dialysis services/clinics.
Concept(s)	Agent-Based Modeling, multi-agent systems, agent-based simulation, simulation-based resource allocation.
Context	Extreme weather events, natural and technological disasters, and severe infrastructure disruptions impacting the provision of renal care.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Inclusion

- Studies that use Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) or multi-agent modeling.
- Studies on renal patients, dialysis services, or resource management related to dialysis.
- Scenarios involving disruptive extreme health events with healthcare or logistical impact.
- Studies that use simulation, scenario validation, case studies, or real/semi-real applications.
- Full articles, dissertations, theses, conference proceedings, and relevant grey literature.
- Publications in English, Portuguese, or Spanish.
- No initial date restriction. However, if necessary, a time frame for the last 15 years may be applied.
- Technical repositories, notebooks, datasets, or documentation publicly available on platforms such as GitHub and Kaggle may also be included, provided they are directly related to ABM, renal populations/dialysis services, and disaster/extreme event contexts. Besides, they should provide sufficient methodological information to enable data extraction.

Exclusion

- Studies that didn't use ABM.
- Studies focused on general disaster prevention, without healthcare or logistical management in renal health.
- Studies focused on other diseases.
- Comments, editorials, letters, and abstracts without full text.
- Mathematical/statistical models without agents.
- Studies without minimum methodological description, without direct relation to the PCC research question, duplicates of studies already included, or educational/generic materials will be excluded.

INFORMATION SOURCES

Searches will be conducted in the following databases and sources: PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore e ACM Digital Library. These databases were selected due to their broad coverage of health, engineering, computer science, and applied sciences fields, and are particularly relevant in identifying studies involving agent-based modeling, simulation, and the organization of health services.

Additionally, Google Scholar will be used as a complementary search source to increase the sensitivity of the search strategy and to identify potentially relevant studies not indexed in the main databases.

Search will also be conducted in grey literature sources, including ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, institutional websites, and in the references of included studies, in order to identify dissertations, theses, technical reports, and other relevant documents. Technical repositories and open science platforms such as GitHub and Kaggle will also be included, with the aim of identifying code, computational models, notebooks, datasets, and documentation associated with modeling and simulation studies.

Sources outside traditional bibliographic databases, will be consulted to increase search sensitivity. The arXiv e-Print archive will be used to identify modeling and simulation studies not yet published in indexed journals. Zenodo will be explored to retrieve datasets, code, and computational models with associated documentation. The ReliefWeb platform (OCHA/ONU) will be consulted to identify technical reports and documents related to disaster response, health logistics, and the organization of services in humanitarian contexts.

Institutional repositories and databases focused on global health and disasters will be included, such as WHO IRIS (WHO Institutional Repository for Information Sharing), for the identification of guidelines and technical documents, and the EM-DAT (Emergency Events Database), which may be used to contextualize disruptive extreme health events and identify data sources used in the studies.

All sources will be used in a complementary manner, with no restriction on document type, provided that they are directly related to the research question and provide sufficient methodological description for data extraction.

SEARCH STRATEGY

BIBLIOGRAPHIC DATABASES

Search Strategy for Google Scholar (via Mesh Terms)

("agent-based model*" OR ABM) AND (hemodialysis OR dialysis) AND (disaster* OR "extreme weather" OR flood* OR wildfire*) AND ("continuity of care" OR evacuation OR "service disruption*" OR resilience)

The Publish or Perish software (Version 8)⁸ will be used for Google Scholar searches with an emphasis on sensitivity adjustment in order to find possibly relevant studies that are not indexed in structured bibliographic databases. The search strategies will combine terms related to agent-based modeling, dialysis, and disasters. The results will be exported in RIS format and integrated into the screening process along with the records retrieved from the main databases, using the Rayyan®⁹ web application. In order to improve the search's sensitivity, lessening any potential indexing biases, this step will be carried out as a supplemental approach.

Search strategy for PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library (via Mesh Terms)

("agent-based model*" OR "agent based model*" OR "multi-agent system*" OR "multi agent simulation" OR ABM) AND ("kidney disease" OR "chronic kidney disease" OR CKD OR "renal failure" OR "end-stage renal disease" OR ESRD OR dialysis OR hemodialysis OR haemodialysis OR "peritoneal dialysis") AND ("extreme weather" OR disaster* OR "natural disaster*" OR flood* OR hurricane* OR storm* OR wildfire* OR heatwave* OR heat wave* OR blizzard* OR drought* OR "climate extreme*" OR "climate disaster*") AND ("resource allocation" OR logistics OR transportation OR "healthcare delivery" OR "continuity of care" OR evacuation OR infrastructure OR "health service*")

The strategy will be tailored to each database, using controlled terms and free-form keywords.

Search strategy for Scopus (via Mesh Terms)

("agent-based model*" OR "agent based model*" OR "multi-agent" OR "multi agent" OR ABM OR "simulation model*" OR simulation OR modeling)("dialysis" OR "hemodialysis" OR "renal replacement therapy") AND ("disaster*" OR "emergency" OR "natural hazard*" OR earthquake OR flood OR hurricane)

A tailored strategy will be used to balance sensitivity and specificity.

Search strategy for Embase (via Emtree)

For the Embase database, the search strategy will be adapted using controlled descriptors from the Emtree vocabulary, replacing the MeSH terms used in other databases. Controlled terms (Emtree) will be combined with free-text keywords to increase the sensitivity of the search and retrieve potentially relevant studies that have not been properly indexed.

The explosion operator (“/exp”) will be used, which automatically includes more specific terms related to the main descriptor. In addition, search fields for title, abstract, and keywords (ti, ab, kw) will be employed.

The search strategy for Embase will be:

('agent based':ti,ab,kw OR abm:ti,ab,kw OR simulation:ti,ab,kw) AND ('disaster*':ti,ab,kw OR 'extreme weather':ti,ab,kw OR flood*:ti,ab,kw OR hurricane*:ti,ab,kw) AND ('dialysis':ti,ab,kw OR 'kidney':ti,ab,kw OR 'renal':ti,ab,kw)

GREY LITERATURE

In ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, adapted search strategies will be used, combining terms related to agent-based modeling, kidney disease and disasters, natural or technological. Multiple search strategies will be applied, including structured combinations using boolean operators and simplified searches using keywords, such as: "agent-based model" AND (dialysis OR "kidney disease" OR renal) AND (disaster OR "extreme weather"), as well as broader variations such as "agent-based model" dialysis disaster and ABM kidney disaster simulation, in order to increase the sensitivity of the search.

The combination of the following terms will be used:

- For GitHub
 - "agent-based model" dialysis disaster
 - ABM kidney dialysis flood
 - "multi-agent" renal evacuation
 - "agent-based simulation" hemodialysis climate
- For Kaggle:
 - "dialysis" disaster

- o "kidney disease" simulation
- o ABM healthcare logistics
- o renal climate dataset.

An internal search of the platform and/or a Google search using the “site” operator will be performed. Examples:

- site:github.com “agent-based model” dialysis disaster
- site:github.com ABM renal flood
- site:kaggle.com dialysis disaster dataset
- site:kaggle.com kidney disease simulation

COMPLEMENTARY SEARCH

Additionally, artificial intelligence–based tools will be used for complementary literature exploration, with the aim of identifying sources, structuring search strategies, and suggesting potentially relevant studies based on previously selected documents. This approach will include the use of natural language prompts to generate lists of sources, organize information, and identify related studies.

The ResearchRabbit¹⁰ it's another tool that will be used for complementary search of the literature through expansion of the citation network of the selected studies (forward e backward citation chaining), in order to identify additional relevant results not retrieved through structured search strategies. Os registros identificados por essa etapa foram submetidos aos mesmos critérios de elegibilidade aplicados às demais fontes.

The results obtained through these tools will be considered exploratory and used exclusively to increase the sensitivity of the search. All studies identified through this process will be subjected to the same previously defined eligibility criteria. This step will not replace the systematic search conducted in structured databases.

STUDY SELECTION

Records retrieved from databases will be exported to Rayyan®⁹ web application for study management and screening. Duplicates will be removed and titles and abstracts will be screened independently by two reviewers. Then, eligible studies will be assessed in full text. Disagreements will be resolved through consensus or consulting a third reviewer. A remoção de duplicatas será realizada na plataforma, seguida da triagem por título e resumo de forma independente por dois revisores. Em seguida, os estudos potencialmente elegíveis serão avaliados em texto completo. Divergências serão resolvidas por consenso ou por um terceiro revisor. The study selection process will be presented using a PRISMA-ScR⁷ flow diagram.

DATA EXTRACTION

Data will be extracted using a standardized form developed by the reviewers. The extracted data will include the following variables:

- Author, year, and country;
- Type of publication;
- Type of extreme climate event;
- Renal population/service studied;
- Model objective;
- Type of Agent-Based Model and integration with other methods;
- Modeled agents;
- Simulated resources (machines, staff, transportation, energy, water, supplies, beds, medications);
- Inputs and data sources;
- Outcomes;
- Type of validation;
- Main findings;
- Limitations and gaps.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The data will be summarized descriptively and thematically, using tables and concept maps. The studies will be organized by:

1. type of disaster;
2. level of application (patient, clinic, healthcare network, region);
3. type of resource managed;
4. modeled outcomes;
5. model maturity/validation.

For Kaggle and GitHub, the following will be recorded:

- platform
- URL
- search date

- search terms
- access date
- repository/dataset/notebook name
- author/organization
- last update
- release, version, or commit (if applicable)
- license
- whether there is an associated article

CRITICAL EVALUATION

As a scope review, the formal risk of bias assessment will not be mandatory; if conducted, it will be supplementary and descriptive in nature.

EXPECTED PRODUCT

The study aims to identify how ABM has been used to simulate the relocation of kidney patients, the continuity of dialysis, the redistribution of resources, and the reorganization of clinics following disasters, as well as to highlight gaps for future applications in nephrology, climate resilience, and health planning.

PROTOCOL AMENDMENTS

Any significant deviations from this protocol will be documented and justified in the final report.

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